

INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN ENGLISH TEACHING

Badalova Zulfiya Kutbitdinovna

Tashkent branch of Samarkand State University
of Veterinary Medicine, Animal Husbandry
and Biotechnology Teacher-assistant of English

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Abstract. This article describes several ways to effectively learn English, as well as some modern teaching technologies in language learning.

Keywords: Language, English, independent language learning, educational technologies, project, interest, activity, interactive methods.

ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ В ПРЕПОДАВАНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

Аннотация. В этой статье рассказывается о нескольких способах эффективного изучения английского языка, а также о некоторых современных обучающих технологиях в изучении языков.

Ключевые слова: Язык, английский, самостоятельное изучение языка, образовательные технологии, проект, интерес, активность, интерактивные методы.

Today, the focus is on the student, his personality and unique inner world. Therefore, the main goal of a modern teacher is to choose methods and forms of lesson organization. Studies the requirements that are optimally suitable for achieving the set goal of educational activity and personal development. In recent years, the question of the use of new information technologies in educational institutions has been increasingly raised. These are not only new technical means, but also new forms and methods of teaching, a new approach to the educational process. The main purpose of teaching foreign languages is the formation and development of the communicative culture of students of an educational institution, teaching practical mastery of a foreign language.

The task of the teacher is to create conditions for practical language acquisition for each student, to choose such teaching methods that will allow each student to show their activity and creativity. The task of the teacher is to activate the cognitive activity of the student in the process of teaching foreign languages. Modern pedagogical technologies, such as co-education, project methodology, the use of new information technologies, Internet resources, contribute to the implementation of a personality-oriented approach in the educational process, provide individualization and differentiation of learning taking into account the abilities of children, their level of learning. The forms of work with computer-based learning programs in foreign language lessons include: vocabulary study; pronunciation training; teaching dialogic and monologue speech; writing training; development of grammatical phenomena.

The possibilities of using Internet resources are huge. The global Internet network creates conditions for students and teachers to receive any necessary information located anywhere in the world: regional geographical materials, news from the life of young people, articles from newspapers and magazines, etc.

With the help of the Internet in English, a number of didactic tasks can be solved in the classroom: the formation of reading skills using the materials of the global network; improving the writing skills of schoolchildren; replenishment of the vocabulary of students; formation of

students' motivation to learn English. In addition, this work is aimed at exploring the possibilities of Internet technologies to broaden the horizons of schoolchildren, establish and maintain business relationships and contacts with peers in English-speaking countries.

Students on the Internet conduct tests, quizzes, contests, participation in Olympiads, correspondence with peers from other countries, interviews, video conferences, etc. can participate in the work. Students can learn about the problem they are currently working on a project. The substantial foundations of mass computerization are connected with the fact that a modern computer is an effective means of optimizing the conditions of intellectual labor in general, any of its manifestations. A computer has one feature that is determined when using it as a tool for teaching others and as an assistant in acquiring knowledge, this is its inanimate nature. The machine can "friendly" interact with the user and at some point "support" him, but never show signs of anger and not let you feel bored.

In this sense, the use of computers is probably most useful for individualizing certain aspects of learning. The main purpose of learning a foreign language at school is the formation of communicative competence, all other goals (education, training, development) are realized in the process of realizing this main goal. The communicative approach involves teaching communication and the formation of the ability of intercultural interaction, which is the basis of Internet activity. Outside of communication, the Internet makes no sense - it is an international multinational, intercultural society whose life is based on the electronic communication of millions of people around the world speaking at the same time - this is the largest conversation in terms of the number and size of participants that has ever taken place. By visiting him in a foreign language lesson, we will create a real model of communication.

Currently, priority is given to issues of communication, interactivity, authenticity of communication, language learning in a cultural context, autonomy and humanity of education. These principles make it possible to develop intercultural competence as a component of communication abilities. The ultimate goal of teaching a foreign language is to teach free orientation in a foreign language environment and the ability to respond adequately in various situations, that is, to communicate. Today, new methods using Internet resources are opposed to traditional teaching of foreign languages. To teach communication in a foreign language, it is necessary to create real, real life situations that stimulate the assimilation of the material and develop adequate behavior (i.e. the so-called principle of authenticity of communication).

New technologies, in particular the Internet, are trying to correct this error.

The communicative approach is an approach to the conscious comprehension of the material and a communication modeling strategy aimed at creating psychological and linguistic readiness for communication. The implementation of a communicative approach on the Internet is not particularly difficult for the user. A communicative task should offer students a problem or question to discuss, students not only exchange information, but also evaluate it. The main criterion for distinguishing this approach from other types of educational activities is that students independently choose language units to form their thoughts. With a communicative approach, the use of the Internet is very well encouraged: its purpose is to interest students in learning a foreign language by accumulating and expanding their knowledge and experience.

One of the main requirements of teaching foreign languages using Internet resources is the creation of interaction in the classroom, which in the methodology is called interactivity.

Interactivity is the unification, coordination and complement of efforts aimed at achieving a communicative goal and result with the help of speech means." By teaching a real language, the Internet helps to develop speech skills and skills, and also provides sincere interest and, consequently, effectiveness in teaching vocabulary and grammar. Interactivity not only creates real life situations, but also forces students to respond adequately to them in a foreign language.

One of the technologies that provide student-centered learning is the project method as a way to develop creativity, cognitive activity and independence. The typology of projects is diverse. Projects can be divided into mono-projects, collective, oral, concrete, written and Internet projects. In real practice, one often has to deal with research projects, mixed projects, in which there are creative, practice-oriented and informative signs. Project work is a multifaceted approach to language learning, covering reading, listening, speaking and grammar. The project method promotes the development of active independent thinking of students and directs them to joint research work. I believe that project-based learning can teach children to cooperate, while learning to cooperate fosters moral values such as mutual assistance and empathy, develops creativity and activates students. In general, the continuity of education and upbringing is observed in the process of project training. The project method develops students' communication skills, communication culture, the ability to formulate thoughts concisely and easily, tolerance for the opinion of communication partners, the ability to extract information from various sources, process it with the help of modern computer technologies, create a language environment conducive to the emergence of a natural need for communication in a foreign language. The project form of work is one of the most relevant technologies that allows students to apply their accumulated knowledge on the topic. Students expand their horizons, the boundaries of language proficiency, accumulate experience in its practical use, learn to listen and hear foreign language speech, understand each other when defending projects. Children work with reference books, dictionaries, a computer and thus get the opportunity to communicate directly with a real language, which does not involve learning a language only with the help of a textbook in the classroom. Working on a project is a creative process. A student independently or under the guidance of a teacher is looking for a solution to a problem, which requires not only knowledge of the language, but also a large amount of subject knowledge, creative, communicative and intellectual skills. In the process of working on foreign languages, the project method can be used as part of the program material on almost any topic. Working on projects develops imagination, imagination, creative thinking, independence and other personal qualities. The technology of cooperation also belongs to modern technologies. The main idea is to create conditions for active joint activity of students in various learning environments. Children are grouped into groups of 3-4 people, they are given one task, and the role of each is discussed. Each student is responsible not only for the result of his work, but also for the result of the whole group. That is why weak students try to determine what they do not understand from what is not strong, and strong students strive to give the weak a complete understanding of the task. And the whole class will benefit from this because the gaps will be closed together.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The introduction of information technology in education significantly diversifies the process of perception and processing of information. Owing to the computer, the Internet and multimedia, students have a unique opportunity to assimilate large amounts of information with subsequent

analysis and sorting. The motivational foundations of educational activity are also significantly expanded. In the conditions of using multimedia, students receive information from newspapers, television, conduct interviews themselves, conduct teleconferences.

The main criterion for assessing the level of foreign language proficiency in the language portfolio technology is testing. The priority of this technology is the orientation of the educational process from teacher to student. The student, in turn, is consciously responsible for the results of his cognitive activity. The above technology leads to the gradual formation of students' skills of independent assimilation of information. In general, the language portfolio is multifunctional and contributes to the development of multilingualism.

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